

Regotron: Regularizing the Tacotron2 architecture via monotonic alignment loss

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Abstract

Recent deep learning Text-to-Speech (TTS) systems have achieved impressive performance by generating speech close to human parity. However, they suffer from training stability issues as well as incorrect alignment of the intermediate acoustic representation with the input text sequence. In this work, we introduce Regotron, a regularized version of Tacotron2 which aims to alleviate the training issues and at the same time produce monotonic alignments. Our method augments the vanilla Tacotron2 objective function with an additional term, which penalizes non-monotonic alignments in the location-sensitive attention mechanism. By properly adjusting this regularization term we show that the loss curves become smoother, and at the same time Regotron consistently produces monotonic alignments in unseen examples even at an early stage (13% of the total number of epochs) of its training process, whereas the fully converged Tacotron2 fails to do so. Moreover, our proposed regularization method has no additional computational overhead, while reducing common TTS mistakes and achieving slightly improved speech naturalness according to subjective mean opinion scores (MOS) collected from 50 evaluators.

Index Terms: speech synthesis, regularization, alignment, Tacotron2, Regotron

1. Introduction

Text-to-Speech (TTS) is the task in which the machine is challenged to generate speech from text. Successfully building such models, is of vital importance for any realistic human machine interaction system. TTS has therefore a plethora of applications, which may vary from typical phone assistants, to apps suited for people with speaking disorders.

Neural TTS systems [1, 2] have achieved impressive performance, by generating natural speech close to human parity. Most systems usually incorporate two modules. The first is utilized to map the input text sequence to some acoustic features [3, 4], e.g., mel spectrograms, while the second transforms the predicted features to speech waveforms [5, 6, 7]. The latter module is also called a vocoder. Some approaches in the literature also aim to tackle the problem in an end-to-end manner [8].

The predominant architecture for the text to mel mapping is a sequence-to-sequence model [9] based on the encoder-decoder setting [3, 4]. The alignment module which is responsible for aligning the input text with the intermediate mel representations, is usually the cornerstone [2, 10, 11, 12] of these approaches.

Finding proper alignments assists the network’s convergence during training and additionally encourages the model to generate more natural spectrograms. Inaccurate alignments may therefore result in non-convergence issues and this is the rea-

son many non-autoregressive approaches require a pretrained autoregressive teacher network [12, 11, 13, 14]. Additionally, common TTS mistakes such as repetitions and word skips are attributed to the alignment mechanism [12]. Thus, for any TTS mel-generating architecture it is crucial to learn how to properly align the input text with the mel-spectrogram.

A fruitful line of research is therefore to improve the training stability and alignments of such text-to-mel models. Various approaches have been proposed in the literature. For example, Flowtron [15] progressively trains and stacks flows to stabilize training, while [16] uses an acoustic model as force aligner for the alignment module. In [17] authors utilize a reinforcement learning framework where the agent is a duration predictor network. FlowTTS [18] also uses a length predictor to stabilize the training of consecutive normalizing flows.

More similar to our work, [19] assumes a prior Laplacian distribution on the weights and aims to achieve diagonal alignments. Battenberg et. al. [20] also identify the alignment issues in the Tacotron2 architecture, and utilize two families of attention modules to address this issue, such as GMM-based mechanisms. In [21] authors use alignments from independent trainable auxiliary attention mechanisms to better guide the main alignment module. The most popular ideas however, appear to be iterative-based and specifically works that use Viterbi-like algorithms in order to pick the optimal (monotonic) across multiple alignments [22, 23, 24]. However, all of the aforementioned approaches, either use restrictive assumptions, or introduce significant computational overhead.

In this work, we take a different approach and directly address both training stability and alignment issues, by adding a regularization term in the total objective function of the Tacotron2 architecture. This way, no additional computational overhead is introduced. Formally, we augment the loss function with a term that acts as a regularizer and imposes the monotonicity requirement, by penalizing non-monotonic neighboring alignment weights [25]. The regularized architecture we propose is called *Regotron*. Our experiments verify that Regotron has smoother training behavior compared to Tacotron2 and consistently produces monotonic alignments at an early stage (13% of total epochs) of its training process, in unseen examples, where the fully converged Tacotron2 fails to do so. Moreover, the additional term has a beneficial effect on the overall loss, since Regotron achieves lower generalization error than Tacotron2. Additionally, we experimentally verify that common TTS mistakes in difficult examples are reduced when our regularization is used. Finally, a MOS evaluation shows that Regotron achieves slightly improved speech naturalness compared to Tacotron2.

Our contributions can be summarized as: 1) We introduce an efficient regularization term which acts directly on the alignment

weights, enforcing monotonicity, with no additional architectural modifications or significant computation cost 2) We show that this leads to enhanced training stability and generalization due to better regularization, 3) We finally demonstrate that increased robustness to common mistakes is achieved by just adding this regularization term. Our code is available as open-source¹.

2. Proposed Method

2.1. Tacotron-2

Tacotron2 is an autoregressive encoder-decoder architecture equipped with a location-sensitive attention mechanism. The encoder takes as input text characters and outputs hidden representations which are fed to the decoder, which in turn generates the mel spectrogram. An important part of the architecture is the location-sensitive attention mechanism, which helps the decoder attend at different parts of the encoder’s hidden representations. The resulting matrix of alignment scores (as illustrated in Fig. 2), describes how well a part of the input, i.e., a character (vertical axis), is aligned with the corresponding generated mel frames (horizontal axis). We formally describe the alignment matrix as $A \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M}$, where N is the number of input characters and M the number of the generated mel frames. In other words a_{ij} is the probability weight that informs us how well the i -th input character is aligned with the j -th mel frame. Note here that TTS requires monotonic alignment, which means that if the i -th input character is mapped to the j -th mel frame then the $(i + 1)$ -th input character should be mapped at frame $k > j$.

2.2. Monotonic Alignment Loss

In order to effectively encode the monotonic alignment requirement we aim for an objective which captures monotonicity [25]. Given the alignment matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M}$, we follow [25] and define the “mean attended position” (or centroid position) as:

$$\langle a_j \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^N a_{ij} \cdot i \quad (1)$$

which calculates the centroid of the alignment weight for a particular mel-frame j . We then use these centroids to encode the monotonicity requirement by setting: $\langle a_{j+1} \rangle \geq \langle a_j \rangle$, where $j \in \{1, \dots, M\}$, which describes that the $j + 1$ -th mean attended position should be larger (or equal) than the j -th. [25] modifies this requirement by introducing a hyperparameter δ which is dynamically reweighted by the the fraction of input and output sequence lengths. Putting it all together the alignment objective can be expressed as in [25]:

$$L_A = \sum_{j=1}^{M-1} \max \left\{ \frac{\langle a_j \rangle - \langle a_{j+1} \rangle + \delta \frac{N}{M}}{N}, 0 \right\} \quad (2)$$

where δ controls how much to amplify the monotonicity assumption, N/M dynamically adjusts δ according to input and output sequence lengths and finally the denominator N acts as an input-based “normalization” factor. If the first term in the max operand becomes negative, i.e., the monotonicity requirement is satisfied, then it is neglected from the total sum in Eq. (2), thus penalizing only the terms that violate the monotonicity demand.

¹link to be provided upon acceptance

2.3. Regotron

The proposed architecture, called Regotron, is a regularized version of Tacotron2. Essentially, we enforce the location-sensitive attention mechanism of Tacotron2 to find monotonic alignments, by adding an extra loss term. This addition, stabilizes the training procedure of Tacotron2 and also gets correct alignments earlier during the training procedure. Moreover, it introduces no additional computational overhead. Regotron objective function L_R is therefore the Tacotron2 objective L_T augmented by the regularization term L_A of Eq. 2 which penalizes non-monotonic alignments:

$$L_R = L_T + \lambda L_A \quad (3)$$

where λ is a positive weighting value, used to adjust the effect of the second (alignment) term. In practice we only tune this hyperparameter and not δ (see Section 3). Note here that the second term is applied directly to the attention matrix A , while the first to the generated mels.

3. Experimental Setup

We follow the standard practice [2, 7] and train our models using the LJSpeech (LJS) dataset [26]. We use a sampling rate of 22050 Hz and mel-spectrograms with 80 bins. We apply the STFT with a FFT size of 1024, hop size of 256 (~12ms), and window size of 1024 samples. Following the implementation from nvidia² we choose Adam optimizer with learning rate of 10^{-3} and train the model for 1500 epochs. We also anneal the learning rate by a factor of 0.3 every 500 epochs. For a fair comparison, we retrain Tacotron2 and the results refer to our version. All models are trained using mixed precision for faster training and a batch size of 154. For any additional hyperparameters, we refer to nvidia implementation. For the Regotron architecture we use the exact same hyperparameters as in Tacotron2. We additionally set $\delta = 0.01$ for all experiments and we only perform a hyperparameter search for λ in the range 10^{-6} to 10^{-2} , with (multiplicative) step 10^{-1} . For our setup we find 10^{-5} to perform better.

4. Experiments

4.1. Loss function analysis

In this section we analyze the loss function behavior during training. Specifically, we illustrate the respective error L_T for both the Tacotron2 (Vanilla), as well as Regotron (Ours) in Fig 1.

4.1.1. Training Stabilization

Fig 1a shows that Regotron (Ours) does not appear to have spiky behavior, while Tacotron2 (Vanilla) appears to do so. Since the only essential difference of Regotron and Tacotron2 is the regularization term, we attribute the spiky behavior of Tacotron2 to the lack of robustness in the alignment procedure, which is also in agreement with existing works [20]. Specifically, we can see that Vanilla Train Loss as well as Vanilla Val Loss are the only errors which are spiky, see red box in Fig. 1a and its zoomed version on the same image. Note here that the purpose of the zoomed version is to make clear which losses pose spiky behavior and which not. It is not meant to encapsulate the whole spike. It is therefore clear that our regularized version better *stabilizes the training procedure* when weighted appropriately, i.e., for $\lambda \in \{10^{-3}, 10^{-4}, 10^{-5}\}$. For smaller weight values,

²<https://github.com/NVIDIA/DeepLearningExamples/tree/master/PyTorch/SpeechSynthesis/Tacotron2>

(a) Loss functions up to epoch 1000

(b) Loss functions from epoch 1000 to 1500

Figure 1: Train and validation loss functions for the Tacotron2 (Vanilla) as well Regotron (Ours). The red box in the left figure is zoomed in the center right of the same image.

e.g. 10^{-6} , the alignment term becomes insignificant and the Regotron objective tends to the vanilla Tacotron2 one. For larger values, e.g. 10^{-2} , the alignment term L_A dominates over L_T , resulting in non-convergence.

Table 1: Generalization and Validation Error averaged over the last 100 (1400-1500) and 500 (1000-1500) training epochs.

Model (avg. epochs)	Val Error	Generalization
Tacotron2 (1400-1500)	0.4121	0.1319
Regotron (1400-1500)	0.4017	0.1232
Tacotron2 (1000-1500)	0.4115	0.1324
Regotron (1000-1500)	0.4023	0.1247

4.1.2. Generalization Error

Fig. 1b illustrates the training and validation losses from epoch 1000 till the final epoch 1500. It is clear that Regotron has lower validation error compared to the vanilla Tacotron2. This means that the generated spectrograms, for the validation set, are more similar to the ground truths (similarity is measured via L_T). An alternative metric, is to measure the gap between the validation and the training loss for each model (generalization error). In order to so, we averaged over the last 100 and the last 500 training epochs for both models. The results are shown in Table 1. As it is clear, Regotron achieves both lower validation and generalization error, which implies that introducing the alignment loss has a beneficial effect on L_T and results in a better performing model (in terms of the objective).

4.2. Alignment Analysis

In this section we analyze the alignment results from Regotron on phrases from the held-out test set. Since our model directly optimizes the monotonic alignment we expect to see different behavior from the vanilla Tacotron2. After inspecting our checkpoints we find that a very early version of our model achieves better alignment in general than the vanilla Tacotron2. This result is illustrated in Fig. 2 where the first column denotes Tacotron2 alignments, the second shows Regotron (at 13% of

the total number of training epochs) alignments and the third column shows the final Regotron alignments.

Although the Tacotron2 alignment appears blurry in the middle (better viewed if zoomed in), even the very early (13%) version of Regotron, has figured out how to properly align and by the time of convergence it is easy to notice that Regotron’s alignment is much clearer in general. The result of Fig. 2 is not cherry picked and should be considered representative of the alignment behavior on the held-out test set (see Regotron webpage³). This result can be attributed to the direct penalization of the non-monotonic alignments in the attention mechanism.

Table 2: Robustness Analysis. Each kind of word error is counted at most once per sentence.

Model	Repeat	Skip	Mispron.	Error Sent.
Tacotron2	3	19	13	54%
Regotron (66%)	1	10	13	42%
Regotron	0	9	10	36%

4.3. Robustness Analysis

The autoregressive nature of attention mechanism in both Tacotron2 and Regotron architectures, may cause wrong attention alignments between input characters and mel-spectrogram, resulting in instability with word repeating and word skipping. To evaluate the robustness of our model we choose two Regotron models, an earlier version ($\sim 66\%$ of the total number of training epochs) as well as the fully converged and also a Tacotron2 architecture as a baseline to compare with.

Following FastSpeech [12] we generated the same 50 difficult examples and manually annotated them regarding three error types. *Skip* errors, in which a letter/word is skipped while the nearby are uttered correctly. *Mispronunciations* in which a word is pronounced incorrectly, i.e., multiple letters are skipped or confused resulting in non-interpretable speech. *Repeats* in which the same word/letter is repeated usually in place of some

³<http://tesla.ilsp.gr:1994/regotron>

Figure 2: The plots illustrate alignments from the Tacotron2 model, an early (13% of the total training epochs) Regotron version and the fully converged Regotron. The phrase uttered is “The jury did not believe him, and the verdict was for the defendants.”.

other. During our evaluation mispronunciations are considered a broader error class than skip errors and are evaluated separately.

Table 2 results depict that the repeat errors can be fully alleviated by injecting the alignment term, which in turn shows that better alignment is able to tackle mistakes of this nature. The number of skip errors is also decreased but still evident, which shows that these errors are partially due to wrong alignment and partially due to model or data insufficiency. For example in phrases such as “64x64” the intermediate “times” or “x” is skipped in all models examined and is uttered as if it was “64 64”. The mispronunciation errors are the most difficult to tackle as seen from Table 2. Phrases s.a. “Http”, “.dll”, “.exe” or even isolated letters, e.g., “c”, are not uttered correctly and the speech produced by all three models, is non-interpretable. Overall, Regotron decreases all types of errors and most importantly degrades the total error percentage, i.e., the number of sentences in which at least one error occurs.

Table 3: MOS scores with 95% confidence intervals.

Model	MOS
GT	4.377 ± 0.097
GT (Mel + WaveGlow)	3.983 ± 0.118
Tacotron2 (Mel + WaveGlow)	3.898 ± 0.125
Regotron _{66%} (Mel + WaveGlow)	3.989 ± 0.110
Regotron _{100%} (Mel + WaveGlow)	4.034 ± 0.106

4.4. Speech Naturalness

In order to assess the naturalness of the synthesized speech, we randomly selected 30 samples from our test set and used WaveGlow [7] as a vocoder. 4 different methods are evaluated, including ground truth, Tacotron2, Regotron_{66%} and Regotron_{100%} spectrograms, as well as the original speech clips. We note that Regotron_{66%} corresponds to Regotron trained for 66% of the total training epochs and Regotron_{100%} to the fully converged Regotron. Overall we considered 150 speech samples and invited 50 evaluators. Each sample is rated by at least 5 participants on a Likert scale from 1 to 5 with 0.5 increments [2]. Each evaluation test is conducted independently to avoid introducing possible bias when raters assign their subjective score.

Table 3 presents the computed MOS, indicating that Regotron_{100%} reports better MOS than Tacotron2. The evaluation also suggests that Regotron_{100%} achieves similar MOS to

Figure 3: Boxplots of the ratings from 50 evaluators. The distributions are computed with a kernel density estimator function.

the speech clips that were synthesized from ground truth spectrograms. These findings are further supported by Fig. 3, which shows the distributions of the collected answers. The confidence intervals do not allow for a statistical significant conclusion, still Regotron_{100%} distribution is similar to the one of the ground truth spectrograms (GT) and Regotron_{66%} distribution more similar to Tacotron2. This also implies that our regularization term tends to slightly improve speech naturalness.

5. Conclusions

This work presents Regotron, a regularized Tacotron2 variant, which aims to stabilize training and generate monotonic alignments of input text and generated mel spectrograms. We directly penalize non-monotonic alignments by adding a regularization term to the total objective function. We show that the loss curves become smoother and at the same time monotonic alignments are produced. Common TTS mistakes are reduced and a lower generalization gap is achieved. MOS is slightly improved from the addition of our term. Our framework is efficient since no additional computation is introduced.

The objective we introduce herein is generic and can be adopted by any TTS system, with potential modifications. We believe that this kind of solutions are in the pathway for tackling training stability and wrong-alignment issues in TTS systems efficiently. Applying our method to other TTS systems is very important in order to establish it as a plug’n’play method in a wide range of text-to-mel networks.

6. References

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